

Exploring Self-Medication Patterns: A Study on the Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices of Undergraduate Pharmacy Students in a Tertiary Institution in South-East Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background. The misuse and unhealthy consumption of drugs is a widespread practice among students worldwide, with developing countries like Nigeria facing even more significant challenges in this regard. Self-medication is a common but risky practice among students. Despite their knowledge of drug use, many students engage in self-medication, increasing the risk of adverse effects from non-prescribed drugs. **Objectives:** This study evaluated the prevalence, knowledge, attitude and practices related to self-medication among pharmacy students at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Agulu, Anambra State, Nigeria. **Methodology:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among undergraduate pharmacy students in the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Agulu. Data were collected using a semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire. Collected data was analysed using the SPSS Version 25.0. The level of significance was set at a p-value <0.05. **Results:** The participants' prevalence of self-medication within the last three months was 90.3. Most (98.1%) of the students were aware of self-medication, with 81% demonstrating a strong understanding. Self-medication was practised by 41.6% of students, mainly for common ailments. Reasons cited included good knowledge of the disease, experience with a similar illness, prevention, the mildness of the illness, and time-saving. **Conclusion:** The study revealed a high prevalence of self-medication among pharmacy students. Most students practised self-medication for common ailments, citing confidence in their knowledge, prior experience, prevention and convenience as key reasons.

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INTRODUCTION

Drug misuse is a global public health challenge, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, where the indiscriminate use of medications is a significant concern.^{1,2} One common practice contributing to this issue is self-medication, which involves the use of medications, either conventional or traditional, without a doctor's prescription or guidance.^{2,3} Self-medication is considered part of self-care, encompassing actions aimed at maintaining health, preventing illness, and managing conditions.^{4,5,6} These actions include proper hygiene, diet, lifestyle choices, and addressing environmental and socio-economic factors.⁴

When practised responsibly, self-medication can reduce the burden on healthcare facilities, save medical resources, and lower the cost and time spent seeking treatment for minor ailments.⁷ However, the World Health Organisation (WHO) emphasises the importance of taking medications prescribed by a doctor, even for recognised disorders or symptoms, to ensure responsible self-medication.³

Globally, self-medication is increasing, particularly among young adults.⁸ Factors like low-risk perception, easy access to information, media exposure, and educational level contribute to this rise.^{8,9} Various studies have documented the prevalence of self-medication among university students, ranging from 54.3% to 82%, with students citing reasons like time constraints, economic factors, easy access to over-the-counter medications, and a desire for quick relief.^{10,11,12,13,14}

While self-medication offers convenience, it poses risks such as delayed or incorrect diagnosis, adverse drug reactions, drug dependence, and

even death.^{4,7,12} Despite these risks, research has shown that even students in medical fields, including Pharmacy and Medicine, may have limited knowledge of self-medication.^{1,13} Attitudes toward self-medication vary, with some students viewing it positively while others recognise the associated risks.^{14,15,16}

Common conditions prompting self-medication include coughs, colds, constipation, and headaches, with frequently used drugs such as paracetamol, antibiotics, analgesics, and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs).^{12,14,15,16} Sources of information on self-medication range from family members and healthcare professionals to the Internet and books.^{17,18} Additionally, self-medication practices often vary by gender, socio-economic status, and other demographic factors.^{19,20}

The improper use of medications has been linked to complications such as drug interactions, adverse reactions, antibiotic resistance and financial burdens.²¹ The WHO stresses the need for responsible self-medication and encourages governments to regulate drug availability and provide proper education.²²

Despite the growing concern, there is limited research on self-medication among pharmacy students in Nigeria. This study aims to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of self-medication among pharmacy students at a Federal Tertiary University in South-East Nigeria, contributing to a deeper understanding of this issue in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Study Site

The study was conducted at the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Agulu, located in Anambra State South East Nigeria. The Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences houses a mini-clinic within its premises. The population of the students in the Faculty is

613 with 140, 136, 170 and 167 students in their 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th years, respectively (population of the Students, 2023).

Study Design and Population

This was a descriptive cross-sectional study carried out among 613 undergraduate students of the Faculty. Participants were recruited from the total number of students and were selected by a two-stage sampling procedure.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Undergraduate students in the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Agulu Campus who gave their consent were included. Excluded were undergraduate students in the faculty who were not present in school during the period of data collection and 100-level pharmacy students who are domiciled in the Awka campus.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size for this study was determined using the Cochran formula.²³ The minimum sample size was calculated as follows;

$$N = \frac{Z^2pq}{d^2}$$

Where,

N = Minimum sample size

Z= Standard deviation, 1.96 at 95% confidence limit

P= prevalence=72.5% (proportion of respondents taken from the previous study by Eyisi et al).⁷

d = degree of precision (margin of error tolerated) taken as 5% = 0.05

The calculated sample size was 306.

However, to take care of those who may have been lost due to the non-submission of the questionnaire and to improve the reliability of the study results, the sample size was increased to 340. The number of questionnaires distributed to 200-level, 300-level, 400-level, and 500-level students was 78, 75, 94, and 93 respectively.

Sampling Technique

Four sub-groups (Strata) were identified using a stratified sampling technique. These sub-groups include 200-level, 300-level, 400-level, and 500-level students. Then, a proportionate allocation was done to decide the number of respondents needed for the study, and simple random sampling was used to select the participants. Microsoft Excel was used to generate a table of random numbers used in the selection of participants. The participants were numbered 1-613 and randomly selected until a sample size of 340 was attained.

Pre-Testing of Questionnaire

Questionnaires were pretested for quality assurance and feasibility in Nnewi North Local Government Area in Anambra State. Necessary adjustments were made. The pre-tested data were not included in the main data.

Data Collection

The procedure for the study was explained to the participants, and written informed consent was obtained. Information was obtained through a self-administered structured questionnaire written in English by the principal investigator and two research assistants, both medical doctors. They were taught the basics about the research topic, the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and how to administer and complete the questionnaires. All participants were informed that their responses would remain confidential. After a brief orientation on the purpose of the study, the questionnaire was distributed randomly to students who met the inclusion criteria and consented to the study. Participants were urged to be as honest as possible in their responses and were allowed to complete the questionnaire within a time frame, after which the principal investigator retrieved it. The questionnaire was built based on a review of pertinent literature, expert feedback, and discussion groups' feedback regarding the survey style, content, and length. The survey was piloted

on ten female medical students and was found to be of appropriate length, clarity, and content. Therefore, no subsequent changes were made. It consisted of open-ended and closed-ended questions in sections A–E. Section A assessed respondents' socio-demographic characteristics and background information such as age, marital status, geographical location, religion, and ethnic group, among others. Section B assessed information on the respondents' knowledge of self-medication and factors associated with the knowledge of self-medication. Section C assessed their attitude towards self-medication and factors associated with it, while Section D assessed their practice of self-medication. Section E assessed the reasons for the practice of self-medication. The questionnaire was administered to every eligible participant.

Data Analysis

Data was sorted, checked for completeness, entered, coded and analysed using IBM Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software, version 25.0. Categorical variables were analysed using percentages and proportions, and continuous variables were analysed using mean, standard deviation and logistic regression. The level of significance was set at a P-value ≤ 0.05 .

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital (NAUTH), Nnewi. The participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses and that any information given would be used primarily for academic research purposes. Only subjects who gave their consent were administered the questionnaire.

RESULTS

Most participants were aged 20 - 24, 194 (62.6%), and 172(55.5%) were females. The majority were single, 287(92.5%), Igbos, 294(94.8%) and Christians, 304(98.1%). Among parents, over 60%

had at least a tertiary education, and the majority were in trading and civil service. It was reported that 108(34.8%) had a history of allergy, while 31(10.0%) noted having a chronic condition, as shown in Table 1

Table 1a. Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
16-20	37	11.9
20-24	194	62.6
25-30	63	20.3
≥ 31	16	5.2
Gender		
Male	138	44.5
Female	172	55.5
Marital status		
Single	287	92.6
Married	21	6.8
Divorced	1	0.3
Separated	1	0.3
Level of study		
200	65	21.0
300	77	24.8
400	96	31.0
500	72	23.2
Ethnicity		
Igbo	294	94.8
Hausa	6	1.9
Yoruba	7	2.3
Others	3	1.0

Table 1b. Socio-demographic characteristics

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Religion		
Christian	304	98.1
Islam	2	0.6
Traditional	1	0.3
Others	3	1.0
Father's level of education		
No formal education	13	4.2
Primary	38	12.3
Secondary	59	19.0
Tertiary	120	38.7
Postgraduate	80	25.8
Mother's level of education		
No formal education	8	2.6
Primary	22	7.1
Secondary	59	19.0

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Tertiary	119	38.4
Postgraduate	102	32.9
Father's occupation		
Professional	81	26.1
Civil servant	104	33.5
Trader/businessman	108	34.8
Farmer	10	3.2
Clergy	5	1.6
Others	2	0.6
Mother's occupation		
Professional	64	20.6
Civil servant	115	37.1
Trader/business woman	102	32.9
Farmer	27	8.7
Housewife		
History of allergy		
Yes	108	34.8
No	202	65.2
Have any chronic condition		
Yes	31	10.0
No	279	90.0

Figure 1. Level of knowledge of self-medication

In figure 1, there is a high level of knowledge of self-medication. The majority of the respondents 248(81%) of the respondents had high, 49(16%) had moderate while 9(3%) had a low knowledge level.

The knowledge of self-medication showed a significant association with gender ($X^2 = 7.238$; $p = 0.027$), marital status ($X^2 = 36.850$; $p < 0.001$), level of study ($X^2 = 14.398$; $p = 0.025$) and mother's occupation ($X^2 = 21.663$; $p = 0.006$). The prevalence of good knowledge was higher among females. Most participants 304(98.1%) have heard of self-medication; 293(94.5%) have heard of over-the-counter while 293(94.2%) have heard of prescription drugs; 291(93.9%) said they were aware of risks associated with self-medication. The most commonly known risks associated with self-medication include drug resistance to certain medication 262(84.5%) and drug toxicity 229(73.9%), and the major sources of information were academic knowledge 202(65.2%) and past experience of the same illness 172(55.5%).

Table 2a. Factors associated with knowledge of self-medication

Variable	Knowledge n (%)			X ²	p-value
	High	Moderate	Low		
Age (years)					
16-20	27 (73.0)	7 (18.9)	3 (8.1)	8.322	0.215
20-24	165 (85.1)	26 (13.4)	3 (1.5)		
25-30	49 (77.8)	11 (17.5)	3 (4.8)		
≥31	11 (68.8)	4 (25.0)	1 (6.3)		
Gender					
Male	103 (74.6)	29 (21.0)	6 (4.3)	7.238	0.027
Female	149 (86.6)	19 (11.0)	4 (2.3)		
Marital status					
Single	233 (81.2)	45 (15.7)	9 (3.1)	36.850	0.000

Variable	Knowledge n (%)			X ²	p-value
	High	Moderate	Low		
Married	19 (90.5)	2 (9.5)	0		
Divorced	0	0	1 (100)		
Separated	0	1(100)	0		
Level of study					
200	43 (66.2)	17 (26.2)	5 (7.7)	14.398	0.025
300	82.1 (25.4)	12 (15.6)	1 (1.3)		
400	83 (83.5)	11 (11.5)	2 (2.1)		
500	62 (86.1)	8 (11.1)	2 (2.8)		
Father's level of education					
No formal	11 (84.6)	2 (15.4)	0	6.690	0.570
Primary	31 (81.6)	5 (13.2)	2 (5.3)		
Secondary	46 (78.0)	12 (20.3)	1 (1.7)		
Tertiary	98 (81.7)	20 (16.7)	2 (1.7)		
Postgraduate	66 (82.5)	9 (11.3)	5 (6.3)		

Table 2b. Factors associated with knowledge of self-medication

Variable	Knowledge n (%)			X ²	p-value
	High	Moderate	Low		
Father's occupation					
Professional	61 (75.3)	15 (18.5)	5 (6.2)	10.915	0.364
Civil servant	85 (81.7)	16 (15.4)	3 (2.9)		
Trader/business man	94 (87.0)	12 (11.2)	2 (1.9)		
Farmer	6 (60.0)	4 (40.0)	0		
Clergy	4 (80.0)	1(20.0)	0		
Others	2 (100)	0	0		
Mother's occupation					
Professional	55 (85.9)	5 (7.8)	4 (6.3)	21.663	0.006
Civil servant	95 (82.6)	16 (13.9)	4 (3.5)		
Trader/business woman	86 (84.3)	16 (15.7)	0		
Farmer	1 (50.0)	1 (50.0)	0		
Housewife	15 (55.6)	10 (37.0)	2 (7.4)		
History of allergy					
Yes	86 (79.6)	18 (16.7)	4 (3.7)	0.323	0.851
No	166 (82.2)	30 (14.9)	6 (3.0)		
Have any chronic condition					
Yes	23 (74.2)	7 (22.9)	1 (3.2)	1.334	0.513
No	229 (82.1)	41 (14.7)	9 (3.2)		

Figure 2. Level of attitude towards self-medication

Figure 2 shows that 190(62%) of the respondents have good attitude towards self-medication; 92(30%) have equivocal, while 24(8%) have bad attitude towards self-medication.

Attitude towards self-medication showed a significant association with marital status ($X^2 = 14.175$; $p = 0.028$) and knowledge of self-medication ($X^2 = 39.652$; $p < 0.001$) as shown in Table 3. Majority of those who had a high knowledge of self-medication had good attitude as well.

Table 3a. Factors associated with attitude towards self-medication

Variable	Attitude n (%)			X ²	p-value
	Good	Equivocal	Bad		
Age (years)					
16-20	23 (62.2)	7 (18.9)	7 (18.9)	11.190	0.083
20-24	122 (62.9)	58 (29.9)	14 (7.2)		
25-30	40 (63.5)	19 (30.2)	4 (6.3)		
≥31	8 (50.0)	8 (50.0)	0		
Gender					
Male	85 (61.6)	40 (29.0)	13 (9.4)	0.625	0.732
Female	108 (62.8)	52 (30.2)	12 (7.0)		
Marital status					
Single	180 (62.7)	84 (29.3)	23 (8.0)	14.175	0.028
Married	13 (61.9)	7 (33.3)	1 (4.8)		
Divorced	0	1 (100)	0		
Separated	0	0	1 (100)		
Level of study					
200	38 (58.5)	20 (30.8)	7 (10.8)	1.519	0.958
300	47 (61.0)	23 (29.9)	7 (9.1)		
400	62 (64.6)	28 (29.2)	6 (6.3)		
500	46 (63.9)	21 (29.2)	5 (6.9)		
Father's level of education					
No formal education	8 (61.5)	4 (30.8)	1 (7.7)	9.789	0.280
Primary	19 (50.0)	17 (44.7)	2 (5.3)		
Secondary	43 (72.9)	10 (16.9)	6 (10.2)		
Tertiary	77 (64.2)	34 (28.3)	9 (7.5)		
Postgraduate	46 (57.5)	27 (33.8)	7 (8.8)		

Table 3b. Factors associated with attitude towards self-medication

Variable	Attitude n (%)			X ²	p-value
	Good	Equivocal	Bad		
Mother's level of education					
No formal education	2 (25.0)	4 (50.0)	2 (25.0)	7.536	0.480
Primary	14 (63.4)	6 (27.3)	2 (9.1)		
Secondary	38 (64.4)	15 (25.4)	6 (10.2)		
Tertiary	76 (63.9)	34 (28.6)	9 (7.6)		
Postgraduate	63 (61.8)	33 (32.4)	6 (5.9)		
Father's occupation					
Professional	51 (63.0)	26 (32.1)	4 (4.9)	6.399	0.781
Civil servant	64 (61.5)	30 (28.8)	10 (9.6)		
Trader/business man	69 (63.9)	30 (27.8)	9 (8.3)		
Farmer	4 (40.0)	4 (40.0)	2 (20.0)		
Clergy	3 (60.0)	2 (40.0)	0		
Others	2 (100)	0	0		
Mother's occupation					
Professional	43 (67.2)	18 (28.1)	3 (4.7)	13.509	0.095
Civil servant	76 (66.1)	29 (25.2)	10 (8.7)		
Trader/business woman	59 (57.8)	37 (36.3)	6 (5.9)		
Farmer	2 (100)	0	0		
Housewife	13 (48.1)	0	6		
History of allergy					
Yes	65 (60.2)	35 (32.4)	8 (7.4)	0.619	0.734
No	128 (63.4)	57 (28.2)	17 (8.4)		
Have any chronic condition					
Yes	21 (67.7)	8 (25.8)	2 (6.5)	0.451	0.798
No	172 (61.6)	84 (30.1)	23 (8.2)		
Knowledge of self-medication					
High	168 (66.7)	73 (29.0)	11 (4.4)	39.652	0.000
Moderate	24 (50.0)	15 (31.3)	9 (18.8)		
Low	1 (10.0)	4 (40.0)	5 (50.0)		

Figure 3. Practice of self-medication

As shown in Figure 3, in the past three months, 181 participants (90.3%) reported practising self-medication. Of these, 91(50.3%) had done so once, 72(39.8%) two to three times, and 18(9.9%) more than three times.

Regarding the type of medication typically used, a majority, 210 (75.0%) used pharmaceutical drugs. Herbal remedies were used by 23(8.2%), while 47(16.8%) reported using both pharmaceutical and herbal medications.

When selecting medication, 155 respondents (55.8%) made the choice themselves. Others were influenced by pharmacists 62(22.3%), experienced friends or family members 46 (16.5%), and sellers 15 (5.4%).

Students mostly self-medicated for a variety of ailments including headache or migraine 203 (65.5%), fever 162 (52.3%), body pain 90 (29.0%), diarrhea 96 (31.0%), fatigue or tiredness 82 (26.5%), menstrual cramps 82 (26.5%), sore throat 57 (18.4%), toothache 41 (13.2%), skin diseases or reactions 51 (16.5%), and insomnia or difficulty sleeping 37 (11.9%). Others include ear pain 31 (10.0%), vaginal discharge 17 (5.5%), urinary tract infections 35 (11.3%), vomiting 54 (17.4%), nausea 41(13.2%), asthma 27 (8.7%), allergic reactions 35 (11.3%), eye infections: 16 (5.2%), and other unspecified illnesses 6 (1.9%). When choosing a medication, the key considerations were: previous use of the medicine: 165(53.2%), price 117(37.7%), popular brand 84(27.1%), neat packaging 79(25.5%), and type of medicine 71(22.9%).

With regards to the source of the medication, most obtained theirs from: pharmacies: 197(63.5%), chemist shops 90(29.0%), street markets 44(14.2%), leftover prescriptions 39(12.6%), friends or relatives 29(9.4%), and roadside herbal vendors 16(5.2%).

Participants gave various reasons for not using the school clinic. These included: never thought of it 48(15.5%), do not trust the services 40(12.9%), distance 39(12.6%), no one is ever available: 34(11.0%), and other reasons 6(1.9%).

In terms of attitude toward self-medication, 109(35.2%) believed it is a good practice and should be encouraged, while 187(60.3%) disagreed, and 14(4.5%) were unsure. Among those who supported self-medication, their reasons included: It is easier

63(20.3%), more cost-effective 42(13.5%), saves time 17(5.5%), saves doctors' time for minor illnesses 32(10.3%), and other reasons 1(0.3%), When asked when they typically stopped taking medication during self-medication: upon completing the expected dosage 153(49.4%), when symptoms stop 134(43.2%), whenever they feel like it 29(9.4%), when the medication finishes 43(13.9%), and other unspecified times 4(1.3%).

Lastly, when asked if they would advise a friend to self-medicate, 63 participants (20.3%) said yes, while 239(77.1%) said no, and 8(2.6%) were unsure.

Table 4. Commonly used substances in self-medication

Variable		n	%
Antipyretics	Paracetamol	24	79.
		6	4
Antitussives	Cough syrups	22	71.
		3	9
Antihistamines/Allergics	Loratadine	15	49.
		4	7
Antibiotics	Piriton	10	33.
		3	2
	Ciprofloxacin	91	29.
		4	
	Metronidazole	89	28.
		7	
	Amoxicillin	79	25.
		5	
Antimalarials	Artemether/Lumefantrine	22	72.
		5	6
GI Medications	Antacids	12	39.
		1	0
	Antiulcer drugs	81	26.
		1	
Vitamins/Supplements	Vitamin supplements	16	52.
		2	3
Others	Herbal medicines	21	6.8
	Sedatives	9	2.9

As shown in Table 4, the most frequently used substances for self-medication included paracetamol (79.4%), Artemether/Lumefantrine (72.6%), and cough syrups (71.9%). Antibiotics such as ciprofloxacin, metronidazole, and amoxicillin were also commonly used, along with vitamin supplements and antihistamines like loratadine and piriton.

Table 5. Reasons for practising self-medication and perceived negative effects

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Own reasons for practising self-medication		
Good knowledge about the disease/treatment	232	74.8
For preventive reasons	141	45.5
Previous experience with a similar illness	183	59.0
Difficulty in consulting doctors/trained personnel	82	26.5
Doctor's treatment ineffective/have a better plan	60	19.4
Always have the right medications available	61	19.7
Think it is a mild condition	118	38.1
Cheaper to buy drugs to treat yourself	59	19.0
Saves time	106	34.2
To do your own part before seeing a doctor	71	22.9
Seeking quick relief	122	39.4
Others	7	2.3
Thinks there are negative effects that could arise from the practice of self-medication		
Yes	281	90.6
No	29	9.4

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study underscore the persistent and widespread nature of self-medication practices among undergraduate pharmacy students, raising important considerations for public health and pharmaceutical education. While high awareness levels were evident, knowledge gaps and unsafe practices suggest that awareness does not always translate into responsible behaviour. This discrepancy highlights a need for more comprehensive and practical instruction in pharmacovigilance and rational drug use within the pharmacy curriculum.

The observed gender and academic level variations in knowledge and attitudes suggest that sociodemographic factors may influence self-medication behaviour. These associations are consistent with previous research such as Kiron *et al.*, which indicated that senior students tend to demonstrate higher knowledge due to increased academic and clinical exposure.¹³ Similarly, studies in Riyadh and Nigeria have shown that female students often display better knowledge and attitudes regarding medication use.^{14,24} This could be linked to gender-related differences in

health-seeking behaviour and information engagement.

A notable concern is the continued reliance on self-influence and non-professional sources when selecting medications, despite the participants' pharmaceutical training. This paradox may reflect overconfidence in personal knowledge or scepticism towards institutional healthcare services. Similar trends have been reported in studies from Ethiopia and Saudi Arabia, suggesting that even health science students are not immune to risky health behaviours.^{2,4,12}

The preference for treating common ailments such as headaches and fever without medical consultation aligns with patterns observed globally. However, unlike studies from Iran, where antibiotics are frequently self-administered,¹² the current study population showed greater reliance on antipyretics and antimalarial. This divergence may reflect regional disease burdens and drug availability, reinforcing the need for locally contextualised interventions. Importantly, attitudes toward self-medication remain mixed. While many students recognise its risks and express caution, a significant minority

continues to view it as convenient and cost-effective. This duality mirrors findings from other low- and middle-income countries, where systemic healthcare access issues often drive self-care behaviours despite associated risks.^{16,20}

Ultimately, the findings call for strategic educational and policy interventions. Enhanced pharmacology teaching, peer-led awareness campaigns and strengthening trust in campus health services could reduce harmful self-medication tendencies. Regulatory efforts must also target access to medications and promote responsible drug use among future pharmacists, who will serve as critical agents in public health advocacy.

Limitations

One key limitation is the potential for recall bias, as participants were required to remember and report past behaviours, which may not always be accurate. Additionally, the research was limited to a single institution, which restricts the generalisability of the findings. Broader studies involving multiple institutions and academic disciplines across different regions would offer a more comprehensive understanding of self-medication practices. The use of self-reported data also presents the risk of social desirability bias, as respondents may have provided answers they perceived as more acceptable. Furthermore, the analysis was largely descriptive, offering limited insight into the underlying factors that shape knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to self-medication. Future research should consider more in-depth and analytical approaches to uncover these contributing factors.

CONCLUSION

Self-medication was highly prevalent among these pharmacy students, despite strong awareness and demonstrating strong knowledge. Typical reasons included confidence in disease knowledge, prior experience, prevention, and convenience. While knowledge was high, it did not deter the practice, highlighting the need for

better awareness campaigns, stricter regulations, and improved healthcare access to promote safer medication practices.

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Author contributions:

S.I.E. conducted the research and participated in protocol writing, data analysis, manuscript writing and review. C.C.I. participated in protocol writing and revision of the manuscript. C.S.A. conceived and conducted the research with the guidance of C.C.I. S.I.E. participated in protocol writing and review of the manuscript. J.E. conceived and carried out the research with the guidance of C.C.I. and S.I.E., participated in protocol writing and review of the manuscript. C.S.E. was involved in writing the protocol and reviewing the manuscript. U.C.E. participated in manuscript writing and review. The authors read and approved the final manuscript and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Data availability

The data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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